

METHODS OF ASSESSING THE INVESTMENT VALUE OF THE COMPANY

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Abstract: The article examines the meaning of the concept of investment value and the differences between investment value and market value. The methods of assessing the investment value, such as profitable, costly and comparative, are also considered.

Keywords: investment value; market value; cost method; revenue method; comparative method.

Determining the investment value of a company has an important role in attracting investment, since the investor's willingness to invest or not to invest depends on the investment value. The investment value differs from the value of the company or business as a whole.

Investment value is the value of property for a particular investor or group of investors with established or specified investment goals. This subjective concept relates a specific object of property to a specific investor, a group of investors or an organization that has certain goals and/or criteria for investment. [1]

The investment value reflects the financial condition of the business entity and the financial objectives of the assessment. This value is often used to determine the return on investment. [2]

The main difference between the investment value and the market value is that it is determined when an object is used in some given investment project for fixed purposes of use, that is, it is the value not in exchange, but in use. [3]

When determining the investment value, quite a variety of methods are used, such as: profitable, comparative and cost methods.

Since the investment value depends on the investor's goals, the value for each investor is unique. Different investors may use the same valuation methods and offer different investment values. Investors can choose among several valuation methods when determining the investment value of an asset. The most commonly used investment measures are listed below:

1. Within the framework of the income approach, the following methods are used:

- Capitalization of income. This technique assumes the calculation of future cash flows, is used if the income is stable and has a projected growth rate and is a common method of determining the market and investment value of commercial real estate.
 - • Discounting cash flows. It is used for companies whose projected revenues may differ significantly from current ones and require calculations with subsequent adjustment of cash flows in accordance with prices at the current date. The discounted cash flow model is used to calculate net present value, internal rate of return and compare capital accumulation.
2. The cost approach involves the use of the net asset method, in which the investment value of a business is determined as the difference between the book value of all assets and liabilities of the enterprise, adjusted at the valuation date.
 3. The comparative approach involves the use of methods:
 - a. Capital market.
 - b. Transactions.
 - c. Industry coefficients.

Within the framework of the comparative concept, the business being evaluated is compared with similar projects and, if necessary, cost adjustments are made in accordance with the identified differences between the companies being compared. [4] [5]

The investment value can be applicable in many cases. For example, in stock exchanges, when selling or buying a stock, the base price determines the investment value, that is, the buyer takes into account whether he will invest this or that amount to buy the stock. The success of trading on stock exchanges depends on the correct estimated stock price.

It should be noted that the discounted cash flow method has been widely used in calculating the investment value.

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